

Malononitrile: A Versatile Active Methylene Group

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Keywords: Malononitrile, Active methylene group

Abstract:

The title role of malononitrile in the development of Knoevenagel condensation of organic synthesis and their new findings are explored in this review. The active methylene group of malononitriles is very important attacking part in the heterocyclic conversions and also having a great potency towards several microbial and biological systems.

Contents:

1. Introduction
2. Concept of active methylene group in malononitrile
3. Methods of synthesis of malononitrile derivatives
4. Chemical reactions of malononitriles
5. Miscellaneous Reactions with malononitrile
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1. INTRODUCTION:

In the earlier periods, the nitrile derivative differs and proved their multiple practices in the heterocyclic synthesis. Furthermore they performed as an intermediary part in a number of reaction conversions. The malononitrile derivatives exhibits the synergistic toxicity in the toxic-dynamic and toxic-kinetic interactions with aldehyde components ^[1]. Some of the malononitrile derivatives shows the significant antimicrobial ^[2] such as antibacterial ^[3] and antifungal ^{[4] [5]}, anti-proliferative activities on human breast adenocarcinoma, ovarian adenocarcinoma and lymphoblastic leukemia cell ^[6]. They also acts as anticancer ^[7], molluscicidal ^[8], anti-inflammatory ^[9] and anti-oxidant ^[10] agents. Besides these the definite complex molecules of malononitrile derivatives by copper metal confers the virtuous anticancer activities ^[11] and similarly acts as G protein-coupled receptor 35 (GPR₃₅) agonists ^[12].

2. CONCEPT OF ACTIVE METHYLENE GROUP IN MALONONITRILE:

Active methylene group of malononitrile **1** analogs plays a vital and attacking role in the heterocyclic synthesis. Malononitrile innumerate the unique interest in the organic synthesis due to the conversion of different functional groups such as ketones, aldehydes, esters, Oxo and amines corresponding carbanions of malononitrile molecule causes very essential for structural and spectral changes ^[13]. The Knoevenagel condensation reaction offers most of the conversion between carbonyl carbons with active methylene group of the nitrile analogs. Their molecular crystal acts as phase transfer in the specific heat capacity at low temperature ^[14]. In the photochemical study of malononitrile **1** measured by the photo absorption and fluorescence excitation in vacuum UV region by Rydberg states. It was proved that CN ($B^2\Sigma^+$) and CN ($A^2\Pi$) photo fragments increases by decreasing the wavelength excitation in fluorescence spectrum ^[15].

3. METHODS OF SYNTHESIS OF MALONONITRILE:

3.1 Synthesis using ketones:

Wang G. and Cheng B. ^[16] have synthesized the aryldiene **3(a-c)** malononitrile analogs by uniform mixture of substituted ketones **2 (a-c)** and dicyanomethane **1** catalyzed by ammonium acetate or silica gel under the microwave assisted solvent free synthesis. (**Scheme-01**)

Scheme - 01

Gupta R. et al ^[17] have build up the simple and efficient silica supported method of Knoevenagel condensation method. Identical molar mixture of different substituted ketones **4(a-f)** and malononitrile **5(a-b)** were reacted in presence of silica supported ammonium acetate catalyst refluxed on 60°C temperature in methylene dichloride solvent; furnished compound **6(a-l)** gave high quality and yields. (**Scheme - 02**)

Scheme - 02

Elison M. N. et al ^[18] have synthesized the different substituted tetracyanopropanes by the electrolysis of malononitrile and carbonyl groups (ketones / aldehydes) in presence of sodium bromide undivided electrolytic cell reaction. (**Scheme - 03 and Scheme - 04**)

Scheme - 03

Scheme - 04

3.2 Synthesis using aldehydes:

Bhuiyan M. M. H. et al ^[19] synthesized arylidene malononitrile derivatives **11(a-k)** by parallel mixture of substituted aromatic aldehydes **10(a-k)** and malononitrile **1** using catalytic amount of ammonium acetate under microwave irradiation. (Scheme -05)

Scheme - 05

Sheibani H. and Saljoog A. S. ^[20] have reported the ecofriendly high speed Knoevenagel condensation synthesis. In the reaction condition, counterpart mixture of the substituted aldehydes **12(a-v)** and nitrile groups **13(a-b)** were carried out under ethanol-aqueous media in presence of KOH or NaOH catalyst at 50-60°C temperature afforded the productive **14(a-t)** derivatives. (Scheme - 06)

Scheme - 06

Rajendran A. et al ^[21] have reported the simple efficient and rapid Knoevenagel condensation synthesis by using ionic liquid media. The mixture of aromatic aldehyde **15(a-f)** and dicyanomethane **1** were evenly carried out in pyridinium salicylate ionic liquid refluxed on 40°C for few minutes occupied the malononitrile **16(a-f)** derivatives. (Scheme - 07)

Scheme - 07

Pal R. ^[22] endured a new efficient method of Knoevenagel condensation reaction by using fruit juice accelerators. The Parallel mixture of different substituted aldehydes **17(a-d)** and malonic nitrile **1** by tamarind juice catalyst in an aqueous media in presence visible light for few minutes afforded the malononitrile **18(a-d)** analogous. (Scheme - 08)

Scheme - 08

Pasha M. A. et al ^[23] have fabricated the solvent free grindstone method of Knoevenagel condensation. In the reaction condition, the substituted aldehyde **19** and nitriles **20** uniformly mixed with Na_2CO_3 catalyst under grindstone method afforded aryl-methylene **21**. (**Scheme - 09**)

Scheme - 09

Tamami B. and Fadavi A. ^[24] have synthesized the malononitrile derivatives **24** in presence of modified form of polyacrylamide catalyst heated under water by using equimolar mixture of aromatic aldehyde **22** and nitrile **23** analogs. (**Scheme - 10**)

Scheme - 10

Lin Q. et al ^[25] have designed a novel chemosensor of cyanide analogous **26** by the condensation between naphthaldehyde **25** with malononitrile **1** heated at 90°C for 2 hrs in aqueous media via green synthesis. (**Scheme - 11**)

Scheme - 11

Basude M. et al. ^[26] have prepared the methylene-dinitrile derivatives **29(a-i)** under water. An experimental section, substituted aryl aldehydes **27(a-i)** reacts with malononitrile or ethyl cyanoacetate **28(a-b)** in presence of ZnO catalyst in an aqueous condition at ambient temperature that gives end products (**Scheme - 12**)

Scheme - 12

Jain S. et al ^[27] have established a new indole derivatives **32(a-t)** promoted by L-proline catalyst. Indole aldehydes **30(a-d)** evenly mixed with active methylene nitrile groups **31(a-e)** under Knoevenagel condensation reaction catalyzed by L-proline refluxed on 60°C in ethanol. (**Scheme – 13**)

Scheme - 13

Gutch P. K. et al ^[28] have formulated and reported the biologically active riot control agent benzylidene malononitrile **34** groups. These are synthesized by the mixture of substituted aromatic aldehydes **33** and malononitrile **1** in presence of highly alkaline catalyst like piperidine refluxed in cyclohexane solvent. They are bio-significant riot-control agents. (**Scheme – 14**)

Scheme - 14

Gauda M. A. and Abu-Hasan A. ^[29] have intended the eco-friendly synthesis of malononitrile derivatives **36**, **38** in an aqueous media. In the Knoevenagel condensation synthesis of aromatic aldehydes **35**, **37** and malononitrile **1** were equally mixed by using lithium hydroxide monohydrate catalyst which acts as dual-activator nature. (**Scheme – 15**)

Scheme - 15

3.3 Synthesis from indole-1,3-diketones:

Riyaz S. D. et al ^[30] have formulated the different substituted isatins **41(a-s)** were afforded by appropriate amount of substituted indole-1,3-diketone **40(a-s)** reacts with active methylene malononitrile or ethyl cyanoacetate or cyanoacetic acid **39(a-c)** in presence of piperidinium acetate catalyst heated at 100°C for 30 min in aqueous media. (**Scheme – 16**)

Scheme -16

Lashgari N. et al^[31] have reported the Knoevenagel condensation of isatins **44(a-h)** in an aqueous condition. These products were synthesized by the parallel mixture of indoles **42(a-d)** and nitriles **43(a-b)** refluxed in presence of silica based sulphonic acid (SBA-Pr-SO₃H) catalyst under water. (Scheme – 17)

Scheme - 17

Katrizky A. R. et al^[32] have formulated the novel dyestuffs. These compounds were carried out from isatin **45(a-g)** refluxed with alkyl halides and DMF which gave N-alkylisatins **46(a-g)**; then further refluxed with malononitrile **1** under DMSO readily converted into corresponding 1-alkyl-3-cyanomethylideneindol-2-ones **47(a-g)**. (Scheme – 18)

Scheme - 18

3.4 Using cyclopentadienones:

Andrew T. L. et al^[33] have synthesized 6,6-dicyanofulvenes **49, 51** derived from monomeric and dimeric forms of cyclopentadienones **48, 50** with malononitrile **1** by using TiCl₄ and pyridine catalyst stirred from 0°C to room temperature in the methylene dichloride solvent. (Scheme – 19)

Scheme - 19

3.5 Using ninhydrin and naphthalen-2,3-diamine:

Taherkhani M. ^[34] reported the indenobenzoquinoxaline **53** in microwave assisted solvent free one pot synthesis. The quinoxalines **53** derivatives was synthesized by the mixture of ninhydrin **51** and naphthalen-2,3-diamine **52** counterparts of malononitrile **1** with few drops of DMSO in solvent free microwave conditions. (Scheme – 20)

Scheme - 20

3.6 Synthesis from chalcones:

Asiri A. M. ^[35] has synthesized the bis-methine dyes from chalcones and malononitrile. A solution of afforded chalcones **54(a-g)** were refluxed with malononitrile **1** catalyzed by ammonium acetate and acetic acid under benzene, the 2,5-bis-arylidene-1-dicyanomethylene-cyclopentane **55(a-g)** are produced. The afforded compounds have found promising antifungal activities. (Scheme – 21)

Scheme - 21

3.7 From 1-[4-(benzylideneamino)-phenyl] ethanones:

Sindhu A. et al ^[36] have assembled the chemoselective elimination of malononitrile derivatives. The 2-benzylidinemalononitrile **58** was performed by the condensation of malononitrile **1** and 1-[4-(benzylideneamino)-phenyl] ethanones **56** by the elimination of byproduct **59**. (Scheme – 22)

Scheme - 22

3.8 Using chloranils:

Hammam A. S. et al ^[37] have formulated pyrrolo[2,3-f]indole-3,7-dicarbonitrile **62** derivatives. These are gained by the reaction mixture chloranils **60** and malononitrile **61** (1:2) ration in presence of triethylamine catalyst refluxed in ethanolic conditions. The selected compounds possess the significant antimicrobial activities. (Scheme – 23)

Scheme - 23

3.9 From alkyl halides:

Diez-Barra E. Et al ^[38] have prepared the mono-alkyl-malononitrile **64** and di-alkyl-malononitriles **67** by using tetra-butyl ammonium bromide catalyst in solvent free basic medium. (Scheme – 24)

Scheme - 24

4. CHEMICAL REACTIONS:

Jayachandran M. and Shriram K. ^[39] have fortified the 5,5'-(aryllkene-1,1-diyl) bis(1H-tetrazoles) **70(a-b)** derived from (aryllkene)malononitrile **69(a-b)** intermediates. The (aryllkene) malononitriles were prepared by substituted ketones **68** and propane-di-nitrile **1** with piperidine refluxed in presence of ethanolic condition. Then further cyclization was done by using sodium azide with ammonium chloride catalyst heated in DMF solvent acquired the final products which reveals the significant antibacterial activities. (Scheme – 25)

Scheme - 25

Dodiya D. K. et al ^[40] have synthesized some novel pyrazolo[3',4':4,5]thieno[2,3-d] pyrimidine-8-ones **74(a-j)** via malononitrile intermediates by three-step Gewald reaction. (5-methyl-2,4-dihydro-3H-pyrazol-3-ylidene) malononitrile **72(a-j)** were afforded from **71(a-j)** and **1** with the help of piperidyl acetate catalyst, then accomplished with sulphur morphine at 60°C for 6 min which form **73(a-j)**. By closing the final step, glacial acetic acid was catalyzed by the mixture of substituted aldehydes and **52(a-j)** furnishes the novel pyrazolo-pyrimidine **53(a-j)** synthons are positive antimicrobial agents. (Scheme – 26)

Scheme - 26

Dandia A. et al ^[41] have constructed a novel indole derivatives by solventless method. The new annulated 2-amino-3-carbonitrile-spiro[(indeno-1,2,b)pyran-4(5H),3'-(3,H)indole]2',5'(1'H)-diones **78(a-b)** were carried out by 3-dicyano/carboethoxycyanomethylene-2H-indol-2-ones **77** intermediates from malononitrile derivatives **76** and substituted indoles **75** titles. (Scheme – 27)

Scheme - 27

Abdel-megid M. et al ^[42] have developed diaminopyridone **82** of nitrogen substituted fused heterocyclic compounds derived from **1** and **79** starting components. The final derivatives **82** were gained by [(6-methyl-4-oxo-4H-chromene-3-yl)methylene] malononitrile **80** intermediates in presence of piperidine catalyst refluxed in ethanol. The synthesized products emphasized the substantial antimicrobial activities. (Scheme – 28)

Scheme - 28

Karimi-Jaberi Z. and Pooladian B. [43] have constructed a novel synthesis of 2-amino-4H-pyran-3-carbonitrile **84(a-q)** series by facile one pot reaction of α,α' -bis(arylidene)cycloalkanones **83(a-q)** and malononitrile **1** were refluxed under alcoholic condition by using K_2CO_3 catalyst. (Scheme – 29)

Scheme - 29

Manikannan R. et al [44] have build up the multicomponent synthesis of polysubstituted pyridines **87** by using equivalent mixture of substituted ketones **85**, dicyanomethane **1** and aromatic aldehydes **86** in presence of alcoholic sodium hydroxide stirred for 10-60 min. Then the formulated compounds were screened their anti-tubercular activities on mycobacterium tuberculosis. These compounds were found more potent activities than the standards. (Scheme – 30)

Scheme - 30

Shi F. et al [45] have mounted the solvent free synthesis of 2-amino-cyanopyridines **90** by microwave assisted method. The substituted aromatic aldehydes **88**, ketones **89** and propanedinitrile **1** are uniformly mixed with the addition of ammonium acetate catalyst was irradiated in a single component system intended the final products. (Scheme – 31)

Scheme - 31

Datta B. and Pasha M. A. [46] have reported the solvent free eco-friendly synthesis under thermal condition. Malononitrile **1**, substituted ketones **92** and aromatic aldehydes **91** were heated with iodized K_2CO_3 catalyst, the polysubstituted dicyanoaniline **93** afforded in a very short time. (Scheme – 33)

Scheme - 32

Desale K. R. et al [47] developed the candid one-pot multicomponent microwave synthesis. In these neat reaction, the combination mixture of methylenedinitrile **1**, aromatic aldehydes **94** and 1-naphthol **95** were catalysed by p-dimethylaminopyridine which produces 2-amino-2-chromenes **96** derivatives. (Scheme – 33)

Scheme - 33

Beheshtia Y. S. et al ^[48] have introduced the novel DABCO catalyst in one pot multicomponent synthesis of pyridine dicarbonitrile **99** by the reaction mixture of paramethyl thiophenol **97**, malonic nitrile **1** and substituted aromatic aldehydes **98**. (Scheme – 35)

Scheme - 34

Heravi M. M. et al ^[49] have synthesized the novel 2-amino-4-H-chromene derivatives **102** and **103** in presence methanesulfonic acid catalyst refluxing with the mixture of aryl aldehydes **100**, malononitrile **1** and α,β -disubstituted naphthols **101** in a single pot reaction. (Scheme – 35)

Scheme - 35

Hasaninejad A. et al ^[50] alumina supported recyclable potassium fluoride catalyst were created and used for the synthesis of benzopyran **106** by using the uniform mixture malononitrile **1**, substituted cyclohexane-1,3-dione **105** and aromatic aldehydes **104** were refluxed under ethanolic condition. (Scheme – 36)

Scheme - 36

Ahmadi S. A. and Maddahi M. ^[51] have developed the 2-amino-4-hydroxy-1H pyrrole-3-carbonitrile **108** from the reaction mixture of glycine **107** and malononitrile **1** accelerated by piperidine under the microwave efficient conditions. (Scheme – 37)

Scheme - 37

Zirani G. M. et al ^[52] have prepared the pyrano[2,3-d]-pyrimidine diones **111** by the three component reaction synthesis from barbituric acid **109**, malononitrile **1** and substituted aldehydes **110** carried out with SBA-Pr-SO₃H nanocatalyst under the solvent free conditions. The final compounds possessed the considerable urease inhibitory activities. (**Scheme – 38**)

Kibon Z. et al ^[53] have constructed the new 2-amino-3-cyanopyridines **155(a-d)** through enaminonitriles **113** intermediate from substituted ketones **112** and malononitrile **1** by the solvent free microwave assisted method. (**Scheme – 39**)

Khalify J. et al ^[54] have synthesized 3-amino-5-arylpyridazine-4-carbonitril **118** series by using arylglyoxal **116** and hydrazine hydrate **117** in presence of malononitrile **1** stirred for 30 min at room temperature under ethanol and water (1:1) ratio. (**Scheme – 40**)

Kiyani H. et al ^[55] have developed the eco-friendly green facile four component reaction. In the synthesis part, pyranopyrazoles **122(a-q)** were prepared by equimolar mixture of aromatic aldehydes **119(a-q)**, hydrazines **120**, ethyl acetoacetate **121** and malononitrile **1** by using sodium benzoate catalyst stirred under water at room temperature. (**Scheme – 41**)

Danish I. A. and Prasad K. J. R. ^[56] have synthesized 3-cyano-5,6-dihydro-2-ethoxy-4-phenylpyrido[2,3-a]carbazoles **124** from the reaction mixture of 2-benzylidene-8-methyl-1-oxo-1,2,3,4-tetrahydropyridines **123** and malononitrile **1** with anhydrous ethanol in presence of sodium hydride catalyst refluxed under desiccated benzene. (**Scheme – 42**)

Scheme - 42

Varela J. A. et al ^[57] have developed the novel series of spiro pyridines **127** a symmetric chiral ligands obtained from dual-cyclization between bis-alkynenitriles **125** and substituted alkynes **126** by using cobalt catalyst under single pot reaction. (Scheme – 43)

Scheme - 43

El-Emary T. I. et al ^[58] have synthesized a novel spiro segregated indole substituted heterocyclic compounds like 3-benzoylcyanomethylidene-1(H)-indole-2-one **130**, 3-thiosemicarbazide-1(H)-indole-2-one **132** and indoline-2,3-dione-3-cyanoacetic hydrazone **134** derivatives. They are procured by the condensation of 1-H-indole-2,3-dione **128** with benzoylacetonitrile **129**, thiosemicarbazide **131** and cyanoacetic hydrazone **133** heated with phosphoryl chloride catalyst. (Scheme – 44)

Scheme - 44

Makarem S. et al ^[59] have developed the electrochemical induced multicomponent condensation reaction. In the experimental section, a mixture of resorcinol **135**, substituted aldehydes **136(a-h)** and malononitrile **1** were evenly condensed in propanol by using NaBr electrolytes resulting in the formation of 2-amino-4H-chromenes **137(a-h)**. (Scheme – 45)

Scheme - 45

Fringulli F. et al ^[60] have developed the 7-hydroxy-3-carboxy coumarins **143** in a single pot reaction in aqueous media by equimolar amount mixture of 2, 4, dihydroxy benzaldehyde **138** and propane-dinitrile **1** were carried out under water in heterogeneous conditions. There are four types of fundamental reaction are stepwise carried out such as Knoevenagel, aldol condensation, Pinner reaction, acid catalyst, base catalyst and acid-base equilibrium synthesis simultaneously monitoring pH scales from starting medium to the final coumarins. (**Scheme – 46**)

Scheme - 46

5. MISCELLANEOUS REACTIONS:

Hamam A. E. G. et al. ^[61] have synthesized pyrazole **152**, pyridine **150**, pyrimidine **148** and malononitrile **145**, **146** derivatives. In the beginning bis-chalcone **144** derivatives were treated with $\text{CH}_2(\text{CN})_2$ **1**, $\text{NH}=\text{C}(\text{NH}_2)_2 \cdot \text{HCl}$ **147**, $\text{CN}-\text{CH}_2\text{COOEt}$ **149**, PhNHNH_2 **151** in presence of ammonium acetate afforded pyroles, pyridine, pyrimidine, pyrazoline derivatives. (**Scheme – 47**)

Scheme -47

Shaker R. M. et al. ^[62] have formulated the novel Spiro-fused pyran **157** derivatives by solvent less microwave assisted synthesis. These pyran derivatives were made by the cyclization of three components mixture of ninhydrin **154**, malononitrile **1** and phenyl pyrazoline-3, 5-dione **153** irradiated in presence of the neutral Al_2O_3 catalyst. (**Scheme – 48**)

Rajput S. S. ^[63] has reported the malononitrile derivatives azofluorenes **160**, **162** furnished by the mixture of 4-chlorophenyl-succinimides **158**, substituted aromatic aldehydes **159** and acetaldehyde **161** with methylene nitrile **1** by using piperidine catalyst refluxed under ethanolic conditions. (**Scheme - 49**)

Ameta K. L. et al. ^[64] have synthesized malononitrile analogous **166** by the mixture of substituted aromatic aldehydes **164** and 2,4-dihydroxy-acetophenone **163** under microwave in presence of montmorillonite K₁₀ catalyst which form chalcones **165**. On further treatment with malononitrile in presence of catalytic amount of morpholine furnishes the required product. (**Scheme - 50**).

6. CONCLUSION

This review has attempted to summarize the synthetic methods and reactions of malononitrile groups. Many biologically active heterocyclic compounds have been synthesized from that group. These reactions greatly extended synthetic possibilities in organic chemistry.

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